

Full Length Article

An innovative filler manipulation approach for low-cost composite coatings on metallic PEMFC bipolar plates

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ABSTRACT

A polymer composite coating for metallic bipolar plates (BPPs) in electrochemical devices was developed by combining an epoxy resin stable in the PEMFC environment with conductive particles. A novel filler alignment technique was used to produce high conductivity at lower particle loadings, optimizing the cost and performance of the BPP coating. This technique is suitable for high-throughput manufacturing and has already been demonstrated in roll-to-roll systems. The coated BPPs were evaluated under standard ex-situ and in-situ testing conditions, with a good ex-situ stability and a low interfacial contact resistance of 20 mΩ cm² reported. The alignment process had a positive impact on coating properties, with the alignment technique allowing a 20 % reduction in particle loading and a simultaneous 67 % reduction in ICR. In-situ results show that coatings are a feasible option for protection of BPPs in PEMFCs, but there is room for further optimisation. Finally, a simple cost model is developed to estimate the coating material costs and allow for a proper comparison with other standard coatings.

1. Introduction

Proton-exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFC) are a key technology for the deployment of hydrogen as an energy carrier. Bipolar plates (BPPs) are multifunctional components used in fuel cell stacks to collect and conduct current and heat in between single cells, separate gases and transport gases and fluid by use of channel structures within the plates. Typically, BPPs account for 60 to 80 % of the weight and 30 % of the stack cost [1].

The stability of BPPs in the low pH environment formed inside an operational fuel cell is a major concern, and BPP materials must be both electrochemically stable and maintain high conductivity throughout their lifetime. There are therefore two popular material choices for BPPs, either metallic or carbon-composite BPPs. Several fuel cell manufacturers use graphite or composite materials for bipolar plates due to their high chemical stability and low cost. In the case of carbon composite BPPs, there is traditionally a balance between conductivity and

mechanical properties. As the filler content increases, the conductivity increases, but there is a negative impact on the mechanical properties of the plate [2,3]. Thus, if there is a way to increase the conductivity of the BPP without having to increase the particle loading, this can be beneficial both for the cost and also for the mechanical properties of the BPP. In general, a high brittleness and gas permeability for graphite and limited conductivity, high weight, and time-consuming manufacturing methods for composites call for innovative and more efficient solutions [4].

Stainless steel (SS) a promising alternative to composite BPPs due to its mechanical robustness and ductility, in addition to high electrical and thermal conductivity in comparison to graphite-based materials. Nevertheless, without protective coatings, stainless steel is prone to corrode due to the low pH environment inside an operating PEM FC, forming an insulating oxide layer that reduces the performance of the device [5]. When high electrochemical potentials are reached, for example during start-up and shutdown, the dissolution of metal ions can

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occur, which can poison the membrane and/or catalyst, or lead to the formation of holes on the BPP, jeopardizing its operability [6]. It is therefore important to protect the SS surface via suitable coatings to ensure its functionality over time.

Technical targets are set by the US Department of Energy (US DoE) for fuel cell bipolar plates for 2025 [7]. Among these are cost below 2 \$ kW⁻¹, corrosion rates of less than 1 μA cm⁻², electrical conductivity exceeding 100 S cm⁻¹ and an area specific resistance of less than 10 mΩ cm². In order to meet these requirements, several viable coating materials for stainless steel bipolar plates have been identified. Noble metal coatings are high performance, as their surface does not oxidise and is stable in the PEM environment, but even very thin coatings are expensive. Carbon on the other hand is cheap, abundant, and stable at the required potentials, but its application is limited due to a low deposition rate efficiency, which makes the coatings expensive, in addition to long-term instability [8]. Polymer-based conductive coatings can be an attractive way to improve the stability of metallic BPPs by providing greater polarization resistance and lower corrosion current density. Conductive polymers, such as polyaniline (PANI) and polypyrrole (PPy), have been reported in literature as possible candidate coatings [9–12]. However, it was reported that oxide layers are formed at the metal-polymer interface during the deposition process, lowering their performance. A more attractive option is composite materials, where conductive particles are added to non-conductive polymer phases, to produce a coating with high conductivity and electrochemical stability. Several works have investigated composite coatings for BPPs, with generally promising results but significant importance placed on the porosity of the coatings to avoid exposure of the underlying substrate [13–16]. In addition, importance is placed on the conductive particle loading and size, with a higher concentration of large particles leading to improved conductivity, and in-situ performance [15]. A higher conductive particle loading will lead to increased coating costs, so finding a balance between coating cost and performance is critical. Previous studies have investigated the optimum filler aspect ratio and orientation for composite BPPs in an attempt to optimise performance. Filler orientation was ensured through introducing shear forces or by applying a mechanical load, [17–19] and it was found that the filler aspect ratio and orientation did have an impact on performance but achieving a specific orientation of all particles was difficult.

An interesting way to ensure good conductivity whilst reducing particle loading is to ensure good in-plane particle-particle contact, i.e. aligning the particles in conductive chains through the coating. This technique has previously been demonstrated for conductive thermal interface materials, gas separation materials, and sensors, [20–22] but has not before been applied to coatings for BPPs in PEMFCs.

In this work, a dense polymer film containing conductive particles is used as the coating system, with the particle type and loading optimised using a novel particle manipulation strategy for improved performance at very low particle loadings. The particle manipulation technique involves applying an alternating electric field to align the particles in chains producing a high through-plane electronic conductivity without having to meet the particle percolation threshold. The ex-situ interfacial contact resistance (ICR) and electrochemical performance of the coatings is analysed before testing in an operating fuel cell. In addition, an evaluation of the material cost of the coatings assessed in this study is also presented where they are compared the cost of thin gold coatings. Together, this analysis will determine whether the coatings presented can meet the DoE targets.

2. Experimental procedure

2.1. Materials

In this study various filler materials were screened for their conductivity prior to the selection for the coating. These are listed in Table 1.

Table 1

List of filler particles included in this work.

Filler	Particle Material	Particle size / μm	Supplier
E-fill-2707 (60Ni/C40)	Nickel coated spherical graphite	14–30, D ₅₀ 20	Oerlikon
Timrex KS-6	Graphite	3.4–7.1	Imerys
Carbon black ENSACO	Carbon Black	3.4–6.5	Imerys
Carbon black and carbon nanotube mix	Carbon black, carbon nanotubes	CB: 0.005–0.1 CNT: Ø 0.025–0.1 L 5–35	Nanografi
CrN NG04CO0601	Chromium nitride powder	1–3	Nanografi
CrN	Chromium nitride powder	1–5	Nanochemazone
Monel	Monel Alloy Powder	1–5	Nanochemazone
CuNi ₃ Si	Spherical CuNi ₃ Si	10–63	Eckart
Cu APS	Copper powder	10	Thermo Fisher Scientific
Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2	Gold coated glass sphere	75	Poter Industries

The Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2 particles consist of glass spheres coated with a layer of silver underneath a layer of gold (100 nm).

In addition, there were two different types of epoxy used to disperse the filler. These are listed in Table 2.

One or more types of filler material were combined with one epoxy to produce a coating. The coatings tested in this work are listed in Table 3.

2.2. Preparation of coated samples

A slurry consisting of one or more types of particles as listed in Table 1, and one type of epoxy as listed in Table 2 was prepared. Epoxy part A was mixed with the conductive particles using a planetary mixer (Thinky, 1000 rpm, 8 min, 1 atm) before Epoxy part B was added under further mixing (1000 rpm, 1 min, 1 atm). The final slurry was mixed under vacuum (1000 rpm, 30 s, 10 kPa).

For initial screening of coatings, the samples were deposited onto a copper foil (0.025 mm, Thermo Scientific) using a bar coater. Samples for fuel cell testing were prepared on stainless steel plates (Grade 316, 0.5 mm, Goodfellow). The stainless steel substrates were cleaned by submersion in HCl (12.5 %, Sigma Aldrich) for 15 min before removal and drying. The substrate was used immediately after cleaning to avoid oxide re-formation.

After substrate cleaning and slurry preparation, the slurry containing epoxy resin and the conductive particles was deposited onto the metal substrate, which acts as a bottom electrode. The slurry is then clamped between a top electrode and the bottom electrode with a constant force. The desired sample thickness is achieved using spacers placed between the electrodes. An AC electric field (50–150 kHz, < 5 kV cm⁻¹) is then applied between the two electrodes until the curing of the polymer phase has commenced. The electric field causes the particles dispersed in the slurry to align into chains through the thickness of the sample between the electrodes, via dielectrophoresis. The influence of electric field parameters on the particle alignment was outside the scope of this study and has been reported previously in [23,24].

Once alignment is achieved the slurry is cured. In the case of the Araldite® 2020 epoxy, curing takes place in air for 2 h at a temperature

Table 2

List of epoxy types used in this work.

Epoxy	Supplier	Curing Method
Araldite® 2020 (XW 396 / XW 397)	Huntsman	Heat
Vitalit 2009F	Panacol	UV radiation

Table 3
List of the coatings tested in this work.

Name	Substrate	Epoxy Type	Filler Type	Filler Loading / wt %	Filler Alignment
Cu_VI_G2	Cu foil	Vitralit 2009F	Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2	40 to 70	Yes and No
SS 316L	SS316L	Uncoated			
SS_Au	SS316L	Coated with Au 3 µm thick			
SS_AR_G2_NAL	SS316L	Araldite 2020	Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2	50	No
SS_AR_G2_AL	SS316L	Araldite 2020	Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2	50	Yes

of 90 °C. For the Vitralit epoxy, UV radiation is applied (Mercury arc lamp spectrum, 90 s).

Due to the proof-of-concept nature of the study, a thickness range for the coating between 50 and 200 µm has been targeted as this allowed to easily achieve defect free coatings with the technique used for the deposition. Nevertheless, CondAlign's technology is based on a principle (dielectrophoresis) that is independent from the coating thickness. With future upscaling efforts, it is possible to reduce the coating below 10 µm, therefore reducing the effect of the coating on the volume power density of the fuel cell stack system.

2.3. Sample characterisation

Directly after preparation of the coated samples, before Interfacial Contact Resistance (ICR) analysis, imaging was performed using an optical microscope (Keyence VHX-7000).

Before and after ex-situ electrochemical testing, images of the samples were taken using Scanning Electron Microscope TESCAN VEGA 3 and Optical Microscope Nikon Eclipse MA200.

After characterization in a fuel cell, images of the samples were taken using a Dino-Lite AM4515ZTL 10-140x optical microscope and TESCAN VEGA 3 LMU SEM.

2.4. Measurement of the interfacial contact resistance

Determination of sample conductivity proceeded in three phases. In the first phase, the electronic conductivity of the filler materials was determined. The second phase consisted of preparation of a coating (containing the filler material suspended in epoxy) on a [supporting material](#) and characterisation of the ICR with a GDL in place. Within the third phase, materials and coatings selected during first and second phase were used for preparation of PEMFC endplates consisting of a stainless steel substrate with coating, and the ICR with GDL was quantified before and after in-situ testing. Detailed description of experimental ICR determination phases is below.

Within the first phase, powder conductivity of fillers was determined using method previously described in [4], modified accordingly. Various amounts of powder filler were inserted into a PTFE cylinder with inner volume of 35 mm³, compressed by the torque of 0.5 N m between two Cu probes of diameter 3 mm using digital micrometer (IP65, Mituyo). The resistance was determined by a DC microohm meter PROVA700. Knowing the powder layer resistance in dependence of its thickness of under constant force of compression, contact resistance between the layer and copper probes can be excluded from results and conductivity of the filler is determined.

In the second phase, circular samples of metallic plates of size 40 mm diameter with/without coating were examined in order to determine

suitability of sample for preparation of PEMFC endplate. After preparation of this first set of samples, the ICR was measured using a setup adapted from Wang et al. [5]. A gas diffusion layer (Freudenberg H23C6) was cut to be the same size as the sample then placed on top of the sample, then the combined GDL and sample was placed between two gold-coated copper conducting plates. A current of 1.5 A was passed between the bottom plate and the top plate. The voltage between a spring-loaded gold pin and the top plate, through the sample, was recorded as the compaction force was increased from 70 to 650 N cm⁻². All quoted values for ICR are recorded at 140 N cm⁻². The bulk resistance of the gold and copper plates, as well as the bulk resistance of the GDL and any additional resistances in the measurement apparatus were taken into account by measuring the ICR of the GDL independently and subtracting the value from the sample's measured ICR.

In third phase, a set of samples comprised of materials selected in the previous step, in the form of PEMFC endplate. In this case, substrate material (SS316L) with/without the coating or plating was examined in terms of ICR resistance, determined using setup comprising digital outside micrometer (3506-100A, INSIZE) with two fixed polished copper probes of diameter 10 mm with insulation on the bottom and GDL (Sigracet 28 BC, SGL) on the top of each probe. Microporous layer was oriented towards the sample. ICR was determined at different compressions of GDLs using DC microohm meter PROVA700. By excluding double ICR of GDL at different compressions, ICR of the sample was determined.

2.5. Ex-situ electrochemical corrosion testing of samples

Corrosion resistance of experimentally-prepared endplate samples was realised in two setups, each one reflecting different possible operating condition of PEMFC. In the first case, a potentiostatic test was used to simulate stationary operation of PEMFC cell while in second, a dynamic experiment according to the DoE protocol [25–27] was selected.

To simulate stationary PEMFC operation during corrosion experiment, the bipolar plate samples were evaluated for their corrosion characteristics in a simulated PEMFC environment through potentiostatic measurements at 1.0 V_{SHE} for 1 h using a Gamry Ref 600 potentiostat. The coated BPP functioned as the working electrode and was submerged in a Na₂SO₄ (0.1 M)/H₂SO₄ mixture adjusted to pH 3. A Pt mesh was used as the counter electrode, and a Gaskatel HydroFlex® Hydrogen Reference Electrode was used as the reference electrode. The electrolyte was heated to 80 °C and purged with nitrogen prior to all testing. All potentials in this work are recalculated and expressed versus a standard hydrogen electrode unless stated otherwise.

Dynamic PEMFC operation was reflected on the second corrosion experiment, using the following procedure. Samples were tested according to DOE recommendations [25–27] for fuel cell anodic conditions using a Zahner Zehnum workstation. Samples served as working electrodes and the tests were carried out in simulated PEMFC environment, 1 mmol·dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ with 1 ppm of F⁻ at 80 °C, deaerated with N₂. Pt wire served as a counter electrode and silver/silver-chloride electrode (ACLE) as a reference electrode. Test consisted of measuring the OCP for 1 h, followed by a potentiodynamic scan ranging from –400 mV/ACLE to +600 mV/ACLE with scan rate of 0.1 mV·s⁻¹.

2.6. In-situ testing of samples

Samples were tested in-situ using a single cell PEM fuel cell with an active area of 1 × 5 cm². The cell utilised two duralumin hotplates tightened with torque of 1.5 N m with temperature detection by thermocouple probes in both plates. Between the hotplate and endplate, expanded PTFE sealing with thickness of 500 µm was inserted (GORE). The membrane-electrode assembly (MEA) consisted of catalyst-coated membrane based on Nafion N212 (Chemours), prepared by ultrasonic spray deposition (Cheersonic) at 60 °C from an ink containing Pt/C catalyst HiSPEC4000 (Johnson-Matthey), acetone and isopropanol

solvents with weight ratio 1:1 and ionomer Nafion D521 5 wt% dispersion in water-isopropanol mixture with weight ratio of 1:1 (Ion Power). The weight ratio of solid to liquid phase in the ink was 1:60 and the final layer contained $0.3 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and ionomer:carbon weight ratio of 0.4 on both sides. Before the assembly of the MEA, the catalyst-coated membrane was humidified in deionised water at 80°C for 2 h. On each side of the catalyst-coated membrane, a gas-diffusion layer (Sigracet 28BC, SGL) was pressed. A porous carbon felt with hydrophobic treatment and thickness of 3 mm (Mersen) was used as a flow field, facilitating contact between the MEA and current collector. The MEA was sealed to the current collector using expanded PTFE sealing of thickness $1000 \mu\text{m}$ (GORE) to ensure gas-tightness. The scheme of cell assembly is shown in Fig. 1.

The assembled single cell was connected to an in-house test bench before purging with N_2 (99.99 %, SIAD) for at least 30 min and subsequently H_2 (99.999 %, SIAD) and O_2 (99.5 %, SIAD) gases (30°C , 75 % RH) were introduced with flow of $30 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$ for both gases. Characterisation was performed using a potentiostat PARSTAT MC with a 10 A current booster (Ametek). In order to minimise the impact of MEA degradation on single cell performance and to highlight degradation of an endplate, modified test protocol based on previously reported studies on in operando bipolar plate degradation [28–31] was used. The cell was initially broken-in for 24 h at a cell voltage of 0.5 V before load curves were obtained using dynamic voltage sweep from open circuit voltage to 0.3 V with voltage sweep rate of 5 mV s^{-1} . Electrochemical impedance spectra were obtained at voltages of 0.9, 0.8, 0.7, 0.6, 0.5 and 0.4 V within frequency range from 100 kHz to 0.1 Hz and AC amplitude of 5 % of cell operating voltage. Characterisation of the cell was periodically repeated and in between, cell was operated at constant voltage of 0.5 V to make comparison between single cells with various endplates and performances feasible.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Ex-situ filler conductivity analysis

Various materials were identified as potentially suitable fillers for coatings. The most important parameter to achieve a good coating performance is the filler electronic conductivity. Accordingly, the conductivity of the selected fillers was examined using the method of powder conductivity determination described in [4]. Results are included in Table 4.

Among the various fillers, three powders stand out in terms of conductivity: Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2, E-fill-2707 and MONEL. E-fill-2707 exhibited the highest electron conductivity, however, as it is made

Fig. 1. Construction of single PEM fuel cell for in situ testing of coating on planar stainless steel samples.

Table 4

The ex-situ conductivity of various powder fillers.

Powder filler	Conductivity / S m^{-1}
E-fill-2707 (60Ni/C40)	1707.36
TIMREX KS-6	65.47
Carbon black ENSACO	27.17
Carbon black and carbon nanotube mix	8.89
CrN NG04CP0601	29.43
CrN	8.44
MONEL	281.57
Cu Ni3Si	2.08
Cu APS	0.51
Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2	668.19

of carbon particles covered with Ni, deformation of the filler under compression (during the conductivity measurement) is expected. This leads to a higher conductivity than could be expected in the coating. For the Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2 and MONEL particles, which are solid spherical particles with relatively high hardness, no deformation is expected, and the determined electron conductivity accurately reflects the contact resistance between individual particles.

Considering the filler stability in a PEMFC environment, cost, conductivity and availability, the filler chosen for coating preparation was Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2.

3.2. Images of fabricated coatings

After particle selection, coatings were fabricated on copper and stainless steel substrates. Surface and cross-sectional images were taken to confirm the impact of the particle alignment process on the particle distribution.

From the surface images of the Cu_VI_G2 samples at 40 wt% particle loading shown in Fig. 2 a and b, there is a clear visual difference between the aligned and non-aligned samples. For the non-aligned sample there is significantly more particles on the surface of the coating, meaning that there must be fewer in the bulk coating. After alignment, there are clear chains of particles on the surface, and fewer particles in total, meaning there must be more in the bulk.

In the cross-sectional images of samples SS_AR_G2, Fig. 2 c and d, some differences can be observed between the aligned and non-aligned samples. The not-aligned coating has a more random distribution of the particles inside the coating, with little particle-to-particle contact and most particles surrounded by a layer of epoxy. The aligned coating is thinner, and the particles tend to form clusters, which might form a conductive bridge through the coating.

3.3. ICR analysis

For the sample series Cu_VI_G2, samples containing the Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2 at loadings between 40 and 70 wt%, in Vitralit 2009F epoxy were fabricated. Before curing, the samples were either aligned (to achieve linear chains of particles through the coating) or not aligned (with a stochastic distribution of particles through the coating). The results of the ICR measurement are shown in Fig. 3.

In this case, there is a clear impact of the alignment process on the ICR of the coatings, with in all cases the aligned samples having a significantly lower ICR than the non-aligned samples. This shows that the alignment process successfully increases the number of contact points between particles and promotes the formation of chains of particles through the coating, providing conductive pathways.

As the particle loading increases, the ICR of the coatings reduce and the impact of the alignment process becomes smaller. This is because it is easier to achieve the particle-to-particle contact needed for good electronic conductivity through the coating due to the high number of particles. However, the alignment process still improves the ICR by ensuring the presence of multiple chains of particles. At the highest

Fig. 2. Optical microscope (a, b) and SEM (c, d) images of non-aligned (a, c) and aligned (b, d) samples. Optical microscope images in a and b show the surface of sample Cu_VI_G2 with a particle loading of 40 wt%, where the light spots are the conductive particles. SEM images in c and d show a cross section of the SS_AR_G2 samples, whereby the conductive particles are the spheres in the centre of the image.

Fig. 3. The interfacial contact resistance of coatings series Cu_VI_G2 showing the impact of particle loading and alignment.

particle loadings of 60 and 70 wt%, the slurry prepared before coating becomes too viscous leading to poor adhesion to the substrate and higher ICR than for lower loadings. Additional benefit of adding more particles is minimised due to the sufficient number of conductive pathways already present.

Results on an additional investigation on the impact of coating thickness on the ICR are reported in the [supplementary information](#). Fig. S1, show that increasing the thickness does not have an impact on the ICR for thin coatings. For the coating thickness above 200 μm , however, a slight increase in ICR is indicated.

In all cases, the ICR values of the coatings fail to meet the DoE target of 10 $\text{m}\Omega\text{ cm}^2$. As the particles themselves meet conductivity targets, the higher ICR must be due to insufficient contact between the particles.

This could be due to a thin shell of semi-cured epoxy covering the particles before the alignment takes place, limiting the particle–particle or particle–substrate/particle–surface contact. In this case, the time taken between slurry mixing and alignment is critical and shall be investigated in future work.

3.4. Ex-situ electrochemical analysis of samples corrosion stability

Ex-situ electrochemical analysis of the fabricated coatings was performed in a simulated PEMFC environment to determine their stability. The potentiostatic and potentiodynamic responses of the samples are shown in Fig. 4. In part a, the response of a Cu_VI_G2 sample when exposed to 1.0 V_{SHE} over 1 h is shown at 80 °C in a slightly acidic environment. In this case, the corrosion behaviour is promising, with corrosion current density dropping from an initial value of 25 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ to between 10 and 15 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$. This low and stable value is relatively close to the DoE target of 1 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$, meaning that a system deposited using this dielectrophoresis technique patented by CondAlign AS comes close to meeting the targets required for PEMFC applications. In addition, the ICR was measured before and after corrosion testing, with the ICR decreasing from 41 to 33 $\text{m}\Omega\text{ cm}^2$, due to thermal expansion of the epoxy improving interparticle contact. Thus, it can be concluded that the epoxy/particle system has good stability at the temperature and potential range experienced inside a PEMFC.

In addition, potentiodynamic curves were recorded to determine the corrosion behaviour of the samples in the entire possible potential range of the PEMFC. Fig. 4b shows very similar behaviour at all cases, for bare SS316L and all coatings. The current density in the cathodic part (negative with respect to OCP) is higher in case of bare SS316L. This is due to good access of the solution to the metal surface where the cathodic reaction might occur. The section in between -0.2 and -0.0

Fig. 4. Potentiostatic (a) and potentiodynamic (b) responses of fabricated samples during ex-situ testing in a simulated PEMFC environment. (a) shows the current density response of sample Cu_VI_G2 with particle loading of 50 wt % and particle alignment during an exposed potential of 1.0 VSHE for 1 h. (b) shows the potentiodynamic response of samples SS_AR_G2 compared to uncoated stainless steel. The horizontal line demonstrates the maximal acceptable anodic current density according to the DOE recommendations.

V/SHE corresponds probably with transport-controlled reduction of oxygen with limiting current density of approximately $8 \mu\text{A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$.

In the case of the coated samples, the reduction current density was always lower than the stainless steel substrate, indicating a blockage of the surface by the coating. Free corrosion potential values are also similar to each other and range from approximately 200 mV/SHE to +300 mV/SHE for all the samples. Curves are identical in the anodic part (positive with respect to OCP) and are approaching the DOE target of $1 \mu\text{A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, regardless of presence of coating or alignment of particles in it.

Therefore, it can be assumed, that the particles do not exhibit any clear contribution to the curves recorded. Instead, the solution rather penetrates through the interface region between the particles and the epoxy establishing on this way an ionic connection with the substrate itself.

It is clear, that the US DoE [25] tests are designed for the BPPs with a homogeneous surface formed by one material. In the present case the situation differs, as most of the surface is formed by an inert epoxy and only minor part corresponds to the conductive phase of filler. Corrosion behaviour of the present samples may thus differ in the in-situ configuration from the ex-situ tests performed. In addition, several works in literature have shown that the potential experienced on the BPP in-situ electrochemical devices is significantly lower than the electrode potential [32–34]. Therefore, the BPP samples were tested in-situ to

provide a complete validation of their performance under realistic mode of operation.

3.5. In-situ analysis

3.5.1. Baseline of gold coated and uncoated stainless steel endplates

In-situ PEM FC experiments were performed with various combinations of developed bipolar plates serving in this cell configuration as endplates. The chosen benchmark endplate was gold-plated SS316L with a galvano-deposited Au layer of thickness $3 \mu\text{m}$. The gold plated steel combines excellent electron conductivity and corrosion resistance with low ICR. The stability of the coating was verified beforehand by potentiodynamic responses during ex-situ testing in a simulated PEMFC environment, as described in Section 2.5. Au coating fulfilled DoE recommendations and was considered, within the scope of study, as a stable coating for comparison purposes. An additional benchmark of uncoated stainless steel represents a worst case scenario if all coating were to be removed, as it is prone to passivation and/or dissolution. Therefore, a series of PEMFC experiments was performed, summarised below in terms of endplate material:

- (i) Anode – gold-plated SS316L, Cathode – gold-plated SS316L
- (ii) Anode – SS316L, Cathode – gold-plated SS316L
- (iii) Anode – gold-plated SS316L, Cathode – SS316L
- (iv) Anode – SS316L, Cathode – SS316L

According to the load curves presented Fig. 5, best results were obtained using gold-plated SS316L on both the anode and the cathode. These endplates were considered as state-of-the-art benchmark samples, exhibiting excellent electronic conductivity and high stability.

In comparison with gold-plated SS316L, use of bare SS316L endplates led to much lower PEM FC performance, due to surface passivation leading a higher ohmic resistance. This can be clearly seen from the slope of the load curve in its linear part and ICR value within an order of magnitude higher than in case of gold plating (up to $43 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ for uncoated steel compared to less than $1 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ for gold plates steel, Table 5). This result was expected and served for comparison of uncoated and coated endplates.

Interestingly, when SS316L was used on the anode, initial performance was very poor, and degradation was significantly more pronounced. In particular, the polarisation resistance determined from EIS spectra, see Fig. 6, was much higher than for all other baseline samples, the results for which can be seen in Figs. S2–4.

In comparison with polarisation resistance, the Ohmic resistance of the cell exhibited only marginal increase. Poisoning of the catalyst and potentially ionomer binder in the catalyst layer by corrosion products from endplate can explain the increase in polarisation resistance over time. This is a consequence of the anode low potential leading to changes in the passivation layer on the surface of SS316L, based on Ni and Cr oxides. These changes result in decreased level of surface protection and more pronounced dissolution of steel components from endplate, poisoning the catalyst and ionomer in the catalyst layer. The formation of semiconductive oxide of Ni and Cr also affects the accuracy of EIS experiment, which can in turn also affect the values of polarisation resistance.

After baselining of uncoated and gold-coated current collectors, the composite coatings developed in this work were tested in-situ.

3.5.2. Testing of composite coated current collectors

Based on results from the baselining experiment, it seems that bare SS316L endplate on the anode undergoes more pronounced degradation in PEMFC. For this reason, application of coating on the anode endplate represents a feasible solution for stabilisation of its surface. Moreover, in contrast with cathode, the absence of oxygen reduction intermediates makes less demands on coating in terms of chemical stability.

The experimental coatings developed in this work were based on the

Fig. 5. Load and power density curves of single PEM fuel cell after 24 h break-in and at the end of the operation. Description of the endplate type is included in plot inset.

Table 5

A summary of the ICR of the endplates tested in-situ, before and after in-situ characterisation.

Sample Name	Anode ICR (mΩ cm ²)		Cathode (mΩ cm ²)	
	Initial	Final	Initial	Final
Gold coated SS316L	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 1
Anode uncoated; Cathode gold coated	6	26	< 1	< 1
Anode gold coated; cathode uncoated	< 1	< 1	8	43
Uncoated SS316L	26	20	8	30
Anode SS_AR_G2_AL; Cathode gold coated	359	643	< 1	< 1
Anode SS_AR_G2_NAL; Cathode gold coated	231	533	< 1	< 1

epoxy matrix with chosen fillers, deposited on the top of SS316L endplate. These in-house prepared endplates were used as PEMFC anodes, while the cathodes were Au-plated SS316L endplates to avoid interference to experimental endplate performance. The prepared experimental endplates are listed below:

- (i) SS_AR_G2_AL – filler Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2 (glass spheres coated with Au with Ag interlayer), aligned
- (ii) SS_AR_G2_NAL – filler Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2 (glass spheres coated with Au with Ag interlayer), non-aligned

The fuel cell with the composite coating SS_AR_G2 on the SS316L endplate located on the anode, and gold-plated SS316L located on the cathode exhibited the lowest performance (Fig. 7). The main reason for this is the ICR of the coating, which was approximately 50 times higher than the uncoated SS316L (Table 5), emphasising the necessity of optimisation of coating fabrication procedure. In comparison with ICR of coating on Cu support, use SS316L support for coating did not lead to good interfacial contact (see Fig. 3). The higher ICR can be attributed to use of the Araldite epoxy rather than the Vitralit. The Araldite was chosen in this case due to improved adhesion to the stainless steel substrate.

When comparing ICR values of the endplates before and after the test (Table 5), the bare SS316L exhibited the lowest value, of 6 mΩcm² before testing which increased by more than four times after testing. In

terms of other two coatings, the aligned one had comparable ICR as non-aligned. Since all experiments were performed ex situ, it is possible that due to structural changes of coating, determined ICR values do not reflect real ICR in PEM FC. Factors such as different swelling due to the presence of water and different compression have to be taken into account.

The in-situ performance of the aligned vs non-aligned samples SS_AR-G2 was evaluated. EIS results of this aligned coating on the SS316L endplate on the PEM FC anode and gold-plated SS316L on the cathode are presented in Fig. 8.

As can be seen in EIS spectra of the single cell with aligned coating SS_AR-G2 on the anode, the Ohmic resistance was very high, almost by an order of magnitude in comparison with gold plating. This is in line with the ICR of the coating measured ex situ (Table 5). However, an interesting decrease of the Ohmic resistance was observed during the cell operation, with the polarisation resistance virtually unchanged. The cause of this decrease of Ohmic resistance is not clear, but a possible explanation can be the relaxation of the coating after the alignment during PEM FC operation or penetration of filler particles to the surface of the coating due to epoxy volume changes during operation. As can be seen in optical camera images, in certain areas the coating was removed during operation, creating a spot with direct contact between the SS316L material and the carbon felt, acting as a current collector. Instability of the coating could be caused by mechanical expansion of the coating during FC operation. Although the performance of the coating was stable and slightly improved in time, both the ICR and Ohmic resistance values were too high for competitive FC application.

To assess the impact of the alignment process on the coating properties in PEM FC, a second coating was prepared in the same way as SS_AR_G2. This time, however, the particles were not aligned in an electric field. Results from EIS of the cell with non-aligned coating on SS316L on the anode and gold-plated SS316L cathode are summarised in Fig. 9.

As in the case of the aligned coating, the initial ICR and Ohmic resistance values were very high. The main difference between aligned and non-aligned coating was, however, their stability during PEM FC operation. In terms of the Ohmic resistance, both coatings were comparable. The non-aligned coating exhibited a slight increase followed by

Fig. 6. Electrochemical impedance spectra of single PEM fuel cell with SS316L endplate on the anode and Au-plated stainless-steel endplate on the cathode obtained after different times of cell operation at voltage of 0.5 V (C). Evaluated values of high-frequency Ohmic resistance and total polarisation resistance are included in plot inset (D), as well as optical camera images of surface of anodic endplate before (A) and after (B) test.

Fig. 7. Load and power density curves of single PEM fuel cell after 24 h break-in and at the end of the operation. Description of the endplate type is included in plot inset.

the decrease after 192 h of operation. As in the case of an aligned coating, formation of holes in the coating occurred during the operation, leading to the contact between SS316L substrate and carbon felt current contact, effectively lowering cell Ohmic resistance. The formation of holes in the coating was frequent in case of non-aligned coating SS_AR-G2 -NAL, but in comparison with aligned coating SS_AR-G2 -AL, hole diameter was smaller. This can be caused by the volume changes in epoxy matrix, which had, in the case of the non-aligned coating, a smaller impact due to the fact that filler particles were not arranged in specific patterns. This then led to relatively poor direct contact between

SS316L substrate and carbon felt. What is more pronounced for the non-aligned coating is the increase of the polarisation resistance during PEM FC operation, which was significantly higher than for the aligned sample. The reason for this behaviour is the limited integrity of the coating, leading to the formation of many more uncovered spots on SS316L material and its consequent corrosion. Formation of these spots leads to the exposure of the substrate to the fuel cell environment. Related release of the ions of metals causes local poisoning of the catalyst layer and an increase in the polarisation resistance.

From these in-situ results, the coatings fabricated in this work

Fig. 8. Electrochemical impedance spectra of single PEM fuel cell with Au-plated stainless-steel endplate on the cathode and sample SS_AR_S2_AL on stainless-steel on the anode obtained after different times of cell operation at voltage of 0.5 V (C). Evaluated values of high-frequency Ohmic resistance and total polarisation resistance are included in plot inset (D), as well as optical camera images of surface of anodic endplate before (A) and after (B) test.

Fig. 9. Electrochemical impedance spectra of single PEM fuel cell with Au-plated stainless-steel endplate on the cathode and coating SS_AR-G2 –NAL on stainless-steel on the anode obtained after different times of cell operation at voltage of 0.5 V (C). Evaluated values of high-frequency Ohmic resistance and total polarisation resistance are included in plot inset (D), as well as optical camera images of surface of anodic endplate before (A) and after (B) test.

struggle for the moment to meet the DoE targets, although coatings can exhibit low ICR and good stability during ex-situ testing. This documents the fact, the approach studied is, in principle, viable. Nevertheless, there is still significant room for improvement, mainly in optimal protective film components selection and mixture composition optimisation.

3.6. Bill of materials (BoM)

A cost evaluation of the studied coatings based on the material cost alone (BoM) was performed and compared to gold coatings. The cost evaluation was limited only to materials in order to assess the cost-

competitiveness of the proposed approach compared to much thinner (3 orders of magnitude) coatings. Fabrication methods were not included in the cost analysis, as the one used in this study is not expected to be optimized for large-scale manufacturing. CondAlign technology has been demonstrated in roll-2-roll manufacturing, but the optimization of such procedure goes beyond the scope of the present investigation. The evaluation included a sensitivity analysis exploring the coating thickness and gold price was included. The gold cost was evaluated based on a thickness of 10 nm, 100 nm and 3 μm, 10 nm being the lower limit reported in literature to successfully protect the stainless steel in ex situ tests [35] and 100 nm a more realistic thickness needed to achieve

high durability coatings for heavy-duty applications. A thickness of 3 μm was used for the in-situ testing in this work. The cost information is based on stock price of gold, [36] and quotations from suppliers for Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2 (1 kg basis) and Araldite® 2020 (12 kg basis). The filler concentration used in the calculation was 50 wt%, 45.5 vol%. The included coating thicknesses are chosen to cover the wet casting where skims of 140 μm are used to limit the compression of the electrodes during the fabrication. The results are summarised in Table 6.

The Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2 based system is much less expensive compared to the gold coating used as a reference in this work. Using the current cost level of Au as a reference, their cost accounts for only 4.5 and 9.1 % of the 3 μm Au coating based on the 100 and 200 μm thick coating, respectively.

The Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2 based system has higher cost than the both the 10 and 100 nm Au system irrespective of Au price point and film thickness. Based on the 200 μm thick film the Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2 coating has 2.7 and 27 times higher cost than the 100 and 10 nm thick gold coatings.

Based on the dependency of ICR on coating thickness (Supporting information Fig. S2), the increased wet coating thickness has a negative impact on the ICR, meaning that the best balance between optimum coating cost and performance for the coatings fabricated in this work would be 50–100 μm thickness. However, the loading of Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2 particles would have to be substantially reduced to be cost competitive with the thinnest Au coatings.

The fabrication costs have not been included in this evaluation. However, production methods for thin gold coatings are often expensive physical vapor deposition techniques, like sputtering. If the fabrication costs were included, it would likely contribute to reducing the relative cost of due to the use of cheaper wet slurry-based deposition techniques. In particular, this particle manipulation method has already been demonstrated on roll-to-roll systems and it is therefore suitable for significant upscaling which would further reduce costs.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, a series of coatings based on conductive particles suspended in an epoxy matrix have been fabricated. Ex-situ results show that the coatings have a low ICR, with a strong positive effect of aligning the particles in a conductive chain compared to stochastically distributing the particles through the coating. ICR values as low as 21 $\text{m}\Omega\text{ cm}^2$ were achieved for a coating of thickness 100 μm and a loading of 50 wt% Conduct-O-Fil® S2429S-G2 particles. In addition, the ex-situ stability of the coatings fabricated using Vitralit 2009F epoxy was good, with a low corrosion current density response during polarisation at 1.0 V_{SHE} . In addition, a bill of materials evaluation has shown that the dielectrophoresis coatings can be competitive with gold coatings of a significant thickness. Furthermore, as the coatings developed in this work are amenable to high-throughput roll-to-roll manufacturing, the relative total coating cost when manufacturing is taken into account would be lower.

However, these coatings struggled to meet the US DoE performance targets during in-situ testing, with high ohmic and polarisation resistances. The aligned coating showed some improvement in performance when operated for 192 h at a cell voltage of 0.5 V, possibly due to relaxation of the coating during operation which promoted particle-to-particle contact.

The results achieved show a positive contribution of particle alignment on the coating performance, especially with respect to conductivity, opening a new research direction in the field of protective coatings for bipolar plates. To reach the competitive BPPs stability and performance, however, additional work is needed in identifying an optimal polymeric binder to ensure better protection of the steel substrate and ensure good stability of the film. The application method for the coating is particularly important, whereby there should be a film of homogeneous thickness without any exposure of the underlying

Table 6

The calculated cost of different types and thickness of coating materials. The current cost is the best known material price, for the gold coating the 5 year high and low columns show the highest and lowest gold price over the past 5 years (2018–2023).

Coating Material	Thickness / μm	Current cost / $\$ \text{cm}^{-2}$	5 year high cost / $\$ \text{cm}^{-2}$	5 year low cost / $\$ \text{cm}^{-2}$
Gold	3	0.369	0.381	0.224
	0.1	0.012	0.013	0.007
	0.01	0.001	0.001	0.001
AR-G2	100	0.037	–	–
	200	0.074	–	–

substrate. In addition, filler particles possessing bulk electronic conductivity, and at the same time corresponding corrosion stability, would provide additional improvement in the composite performance. This will be a subject of further study.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Katie McCay: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation. **Martin Prokop:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Øyvind Alsos:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Anita Hamar Reksten:** Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation. **Miroslav Hala:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Jakub Ludvík:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Nikita Thind:** Investigation. **Marie-Audrey Raux:** Investigation. **Christelle Denonville:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Farhad Torkzad:** Investigation. **Sigrid Lædre:** Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Luca Ansaloni:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Milan Kouril:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Karel Bouzek:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2025.136686>.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

- [1] Thompson ST, et al. Direct hydrogen fuel cell electric vehicle cost analysis: system and high-volume manufacturing description, validation, and outlook. *J Power Sources* 2018;399:304–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JPOWSOUR.2018.07.100>.
- [2] A. Tang, L. Crisci, L. Bonville, and J. Jankovic, "An overview of bipolar plates in proton exchange membrane fuel cells," 2021. doi: 10.1063/5.0031447.
- [3] Planes E, Flandin L, Alberola N. Polymer composites bipolar plates for PEMFCs. *Energy Procedia* 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2012.03.031>.
- [4] Hala M, Mališ J, Paidar M, Bouzek K. Characterization of commercial polymer-carbon composite bipolar plates used in PEM fuel cells. *Membranes (Basel)* 2022;12(11):1050. <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes12111050>.
- [5] Wang H, Sweikart MA, Turner JA. Stainless steel as bipolar plate material for polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cells. *J Power Sources* 2003;115(2):243–51. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753\(03\)00023-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753(03)00023-5).
- [6] Sulek M, Adams J, Kaberline S, Ricketts M, Waldecker JR. In situ metal ion contamination and the effects on proton exchange membrane fuel cell performance. *J Power Sources* 2011;196(21):8967–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2011.01.086>.
- [7] Drive U. *Fuel Cell Technical Team Roadmap 2017*.
- [8] P. Yi, D. Zhang, D. Qiu, L. Peng, and X. Lai, "Carbon-based coatings for metallic bipolar plates used in proton exchange membrane fuel cells," 2019. doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.01.176.
- [9] Hermas AA, Nakayama M, Ogura K. Enrichment of chromium-content in passive layers on stainless steel coated with polyaniline. *Electrochim Acta* 2005;50(10). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2004.09.008>.
- [10] Mawdsley JR, et al. Composite-coated aluminum bipolar plates for PEM fuel cells. *J Power Sources* 2013;231:106–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2012.12.074>.
- [11] Liu R, Jia Q, Zhang B, Lai Z, Chen L. Protective coatings for metal bipolar plates of fuel cells: a review. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2022;47(54):22915–37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2022.05.078>.
- [12] Gao X, et al. Research progress and prospect of the materials of bipolar plates for proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs). *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2024;50: 711–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2023.09.005>.
- [13] Husby H, Kongstein OE, Oedegaard A, Seland F. Carbon-polymer composite coatings for PEM fuel cell bipolar plates. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2014;39(2):951–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2013.10.115>.
- [14] Cooper L, El-Kharouf A. Titanium nitride polyaniline bilayer coating for metallic bipolar plates used in polymer electrolyte fuel cells. *Fuel Cells* 2020;20(4). <https://doi.org/10.1002/fuce.201900200>.
- [15] Show Y, Nakashima T, Fukami Y. Anticorrosion coating of carbon nanotube/polytetrafluoroethylene composite film on the stainless steel bipolar plate for proton exchange membrane fuel cells. *J Nanomater* 2013;2013. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/378752>.
- [16] Ma X, Wang T, Gong B, Cao H. Fast and low-cost deposition strategy for constructing amorphous carbon layer toward corrosion protection on aluminum alloy bipolar plates in proton exchange membrane fuel cell environments. *J Power Sources* 2024;623:235479. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JPOWSOUR.2024.235479>.
- [17] Radzuan NAM, Sulong AB, Somalu MR. Influence the filler orientation on the performance of bipolar plate. *Sains Malays* 2019;48(3). <https://doi.org/10.17576/jsm-2019-4803-21>.
- [18] Mohd Radzuan NA, Yusuf Zakaria M, Sulong AB, Sahari J. The effect of milled carbon fibre filler on electrical conductivity in highly conductive polymer composites. *Compos B Eng* 2017;110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2016.11.021>.
- [19] Heo SI, Yun JC, Oh KS, Han KS. Influence of particle size and shape on electrical and mechanical properties of graphite reinforced conductive polymer composites for the bipolar plate of PEM fuel cells. *Adv Compos Mater: Off J Japan Soc Compos Mater* 2006;15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1163/156855106776829356>.
- [20] M. Buchanan, M. Knaapila, G. Helgesen, and H. Hoeyer, "Method for assembling conductive particles into conductive pathways and sensors thus formed," US10071902B2, 2018.
- [21] Jones D. *Commercialising research in advanced materials and sustainable manufacturing*. *Johnson Matthey Technol Rev* 2019;63(4):277–80.
- [22] M. A. Raux, P. A. Hassel, L. Sorvik, P. Mayhew, and H. Hemmen, An Innovative Way to Make Anisotropic Thermal Interface Materials, in: *InterSociety Conference on Thermal and Thermomechanical Phenomena in Electronic Systems, ITherm*, 2020. doi: 10.1109/ITherm45881.2020.9190254.
- [23] H. Hemmen et al., "Bipolar Plate," European Patent Application Number EP23197537.6, 2023.
- [24] M. Knaapila, M. Buchanan, and G. Helgesen, "Anisotropic conductive polymer material," 10090076, 2011.
- [25] U. US Department of Energy office of energy efficiency and renewable energy, "US DOE Technical Targets for Polymer Electrolyte Membrane Fuel Cell Components." Accessed: Aug. 10, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://energy.gov/eere/fuelcells/doe-technical-targets-polymer-electrolyte-membrane-fuel-cell-components>.
- [26] R. Borup et al., "(Metal) Bipolar Plate Testing - DOE 2017 Bipolar Plates Workshop," 2017.
- [27] Hirano S. *R&D for Automotive PEM Fuel Cell System-Bipolar Plates*. MI: Southfield; 2017.
- [28] Hung Y, El-Khatib KM, Tawfik H. Testing and evaluation of aluminum coated bipolar plates of pem fuel cells operating at 70 °C. *J Power Sources* 2006;163(1): 509–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JPOWSOUR.2006.09.013>.
- [29] Tawfik H, Hung Y, Mahajan D. Metal bipolar plates for PEM fuel cell—a review. *J Power Sources* 2007;163(2):755–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JPOWSOUR.2006.09.088>.
- [30] Matsuura T, Kato M, Hori M. Study on metallic bipolar plate for proton exchange membrane fuel cell. *J Power Sources* 2006;161(1):74–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JPOWSOUR.2006.04.064>.
- [31] Wind J, Späh R, Kaiser W, Böhm G. Metallic bipolar plates for PEM fuel cells. *J Power Sources* 2002;105(2):256–60. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753\(01\)00950-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753(01)00950-8).
- [32] Orsi A, Kongstein OE, Hamilton PJ, Oedegaard A, Svenum IH, Cooke K. An investigation of the typical corrosion parameters used to test polymer electrolyte fuel cell bipolar plate coatings, with titanium nitride coated stainless steel as a case study. *J Power Sources* 2015;285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2015.03.111>.
- [33] Hinds G, Brightman E. Towards more representative test methods for corrosion resistance of PEMFC metallic bipolar plates. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2015;40(6): 2785–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2014.12.085>.
- [34] Becker H, et al. Assessing potential profiles in water electrolyzers to minimise titanium use. *Energy Environ Sci* 2022;15(6). <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2ee00876a>.
- [35] Kumar A, Ricketts M, Hirano S. Ex situ evaluation of nanometer range gold coating on stainless steel substrate for automotive polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cell bipolar plate. *J Power Sources* 2010;195(5):1401–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2009.09.022>.
- [36] "Gold Price Chart, www.bullionvault.com, accessed 21/05/2023."